

КУЛЬТУРА И ЦИВИЛИЗАЦИЯ / CULTURE AND CIVILIZATION

УДК 5.10.1.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10967903

THE LANGUAGE OF POLITICAL CAMPAIGNS. CULTURAL SPECIFICITIES AND EXPRESSIVE MEANS OF THE LANGUAGE IN CORRELATION WITH THE METHODS OF TRANSLATION OF 2000-2020 BRITISH AND AMERICAN ELECTION CAMPAIGNS FROM ENGLISH INTO RUSSIAN

Madina T. ARCHAKOVA,

National Research Moscow State University of Civil Engineering (MGSU) (Moscow, Russia);

Lecturer; e-mail: archakovam27@gmail.com

Abstract. In the modern world politics play an immensely important role, determining social, economic, humanitarian and cultural development of countries. Democratization of state institutions and rapid development of information technologies, have created new ways for citizens to participate in the political life of the country. This function is executed by political advertising. To meet the many different needs that contributed to the emergence of the phenomenon of political advertising, and due to the development of new technology, the media and the Internet, rapid, widespread changes in political advertising have occurred, it has actualized and new types and classifications have appeared. In the context of globalization, when people from different parts of the world and cultures are becoming closer to each other, there is a need to reduce the communication gap by studying the worldview of people who speak different languages. This is facilitated by quality translation that takes into account all the subtleties of highly imaginative texts, which include political advertising. The aim of the study is to find ways to translate political speeches into Russian preserving the style and linguocultural peculiarities of political texts of various genres, while retaining their semantic and pragmatic functions. The subject of the study is linguocultural peculiarities of political campaigns, explicit and implicit means of presenting information, linguistic ways of achieving perlocutionary effect and suggestive methods of manipulating public opinion, as well as various methods of translating political advertisements of different genres from English into Russian without loss of imagery or layers of meaning. The object of the study is political advertising in the US and UK in years 2000 to 2020. Included in this article are some of the examples of the use of culture-specific elements in different genres of political advertising in the US and the UK and their translation, which are part of a larger ongoing study by the same author.

Keywords: political advertising, culture-specific elements, specificity, translation, discourse, techniques, adaptation, imagery, stylistic devices

For citation: Archakova, M.T. (2024). The language of political campaigns. Cultural specificities and expressive means of the language in correlation with the methods of translation of 2000-2020 British and American election campaigns from English into Russian. Service plus, 18(1), 3-12. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10967903.

Submitted: 2024/01/30.

Accepted: 2024/03/20.

ЯЗЫК ПОЛИТИЧЕСКОЙ РЕКЛАМЫ. СПЕЦИФИКА ПЕРЕДАЧИ КУЛЬТУРНЫХ РЕАЛИЙ И ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКИХ СРЕДСТВ ВЫРАЗИТЕЛЬНОСТИ, ИСПОЛЬЗУЕМЫХ В АНГЛОЯЗЫЧНОЙ ПРЕДВЫБОРНОЙ ПОЛИТИЧЕСКОЙ РЕКЛАМЕ НА РУССКИЙ ЯЗЫК (НА МАТЕРИАЛЕ ПОЛИТИЧЕСКИХ КАМПАНИЙ США И ВЕЛИКОБРИТАНИИ 2000-2020 ГОДОВ)

АРЧАКОВА Мадина Тархановна,

Национальный исследовательский Московский государственный строительный университет (Москва, РФ);
Преподаватель; e-mail: archakovam27@gmail.com

Аннотация. В современном мире политика играет огромную роль, определяя направление социального, экономического, гуманитарного и культурного развития государств. В условиях демократизации государственных институтов и стремительного развития информационных технологий появляются все новые способы участия граждан в политической жизни страны, а значит, также усиливается необходимость эффективного диалога между политиками и их избирателями. Эту функцию берет на себя политическая реклама. Необходимость удовлетворения множества различных потребностей, способствовавших зарождению феномена политической рекламы, а также появление новых технологий и развитие СМИ и сети-интернет, привели к стремительным и повсеместным изменениям в области политической рекламы, произошла ее актуализация и появились новые виды и классификации. В условиях глобализации, когда люди разных стран и культур становятся ближе друг к другу, появляется необходимость сокращения коммуникационного разрыва посредством изучения картины мира людей, говорящих на разных языках. Этому способствует качественный перевод, учитывающий все тонкости текстов высокой образности, к которым относится политическая реклама. Цель исследования заключается в том, чтобы подобрать способы перевода политической рекламы на русский язык с сохранением как стиля и лингвокультурных особенностей политической рекламы различных жанров, так и ее семантической и прагматической функций. Предметом исследования являются лингвокультурные особенности политической рекламы, используемые в ней эксплицитные и имплицитные средства подачи информации, лингвистические способы достижения перлокутивного эффекта и суггестивные способы манипуляции общественным мнением, а также приемы передачи различных рекламных жанров с английского на русский язык. Объектом исследования является политическая реклама в США и Великобритании в период с 2000-го по 2020-й год. В данной статье будут представлены некоторые примеры использования культурных реалий в различных жанрах политической рекламы в США и Великобритании и способы их перевода, которые являются частью более обширного продолжающегося исследования того же автора.

Ключевые слова: политическая реклама, культурные реалии, специфика, перевод, дискурс, приемы, адаптация, образность, лингвистические средства

Для цитирования: Арчакова М.Т. Язык политической рекламы. Специфика передачи культурных реалий и лингвистических средств выразительности, используемых в англоязычной предвыборной политической рекламе на русский язык (на материале политических кампаний США и Великобритании 2000-2020 годов). // *Service plus*. 2024. Т. 18. №1. С.3-12. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10967903.

Статья поступила в редакцию: 30.01.2024.

Статья принята к публикации: 20.03.2024.

Introduction

In the modern world, politics are essential to determining the vectors of social, economic, humanitarian and cultural development of states. The sixth technological order contributes to the democratization of state institutions in the world, the spread of information technology, which means that access to information is rapidly increasing, and new opportunities for citizens to participate in state governance are opening up. Thus, there is a need to create and develop effective mechanisms for regulating political, social and economic relations between the civil society and those who represent state institutions of power. Political communication, and more broadly - political discourse - acts as one of such mechanisms, polymodality and aestheticization of which is observed in the speeches of political figures [1, p. 128]. In its current state, interdisciplinary has become a prevalent characteristic feature of political linguistics.

Competitive struggle for public consciousness in the conditions of democracy and the conduct of open and free elections serves to evolve the array of mechanisms aimed at educating and persuading voters, shaping their behavioral patterns, and ultimately creating a predisposition to support a specific political party or candidate. Political advertising is one of the oldest and most effective tools in the race to win the electorate's votes. It has existed since the first states were formed and there was a division of people into politicians and ordinary citizens, since they needed to maintain a dialog with each other.

Political advertising: objectives, characteristics, language

Political advertising encompasses a diverse array of functions, demonstrating both constructive and detrimental implications. On the positive side, it serves as a means of sharing information, and aides the voters in making well-informed decisions regarding their chosen representatives. Conversely, the negative aspect involves the potential for exploitation and psychological influence for self-serving objectives. Furthermore, with the progression of technology, novel forms of political advertising are continually emerging, along with more potent methods for politicians to establish connections with the citizens. This paper will examine

the discourse of political advertising, overview the history and current state of political advertising through the prism of linguistic devices and culturally specific characteristics of advertising campaigns of US presidents and British prime ministers, as well as present translation techniques and linguacultural adaptation of advertising texts from English into Russian¹.

In political discourse, several characteristic features are discernible. Foremost, the predominant addressee is mass, indicating a widespread reach of the message. Moreover, emotional appeal plays a significant role, often taking precedence over rational argumentation. Additionally, the use of manipulative strategies contributes to the esoteric nature of political discourse, leading to a sense of exclusivity and hidden agendas. It is also marked by dynamism of language; theatricality; indirectness. [2, p. 344].

Political advertising has the following attributes: the subject of advertising is named, its positive qualities are described, a positive result is planned [3, p. 304].

Political discourse fulfills the function of influence, combined with the informational component. Information in political discourse is heterogeneous, it is represented by the factual component, but also by the component of generalization and imagery [4, p. 145]. The expressiveness of the message is better perceived in oral form, and facts and arguments - in writing. Radio and television are considered to be media of low engagement, while print media are considered to be of high engagement.

The linguistic component of political discourse should be accessible, understandable and engaging. In political discourse, the audience's attention is drawn through the coverage of events close to them, the information is constantly supplemented with new facts and opinions [5, p. 133-134].

In political advertising, communication is often carried out by means of directives or commissives, as well as promissive intension, which express a promise, and menassives, which are speech acts of threat [6, p. 85,89].

For political discourse, the regulative function, namely the one that contains the idea of realizing the will of the addresser, attempts to influence the ad-

¹ Abridged by the author.

dressee, is fundamental, as it marks the role of language in regulating the actions of the recipient of the message². The aforementioned function is precisely the one political advertising is set to perform: use various methods of manipulating information, verbally and non-verbally, to incline the addressee towards a certain decision or conclusion.

In political discourse, the choice of linguistic devices is very important, which is never random, it is an act of subjective evaluation [7, p. 431]. Lexical units contain information about both the subject of communication and its participants. Nuanced semantic interpretations and connotations play a substantial role in the successful outcome of communication, using the aforementioned, the speaker expresses their subjective attitude to the communicative situation. According to researcher Chernyavskaya, denotative meaning can change depending on the emotional component attached to the words. Thus, certain lexical elements transfer the speaker's point of view onto the subject and form the opinion of the recipients, thus making language a powerful tool of manipulation.

Chernyavskaya defines manipulation as the hidden introduction of wishes, attitudes and intentions into the addressee's consciousness in order to realize the interests of the message sender, which do not necessarily coincide with the interests of the addressee [8, p. 19].

In linguistics such terms as "persuasiveness" and "suggestiveness" are used to reflect the idea of linguistic influence. According to Chernyavskaya, persuasiveness is the impact of the author of an oral or written message on its addressee in order to persuade or call for an action [8, p. 25]. Persuasiveness implies that the message is consciously composed in such a way as to influence the recipient or induce them to act. Suggestiveness is characterized by the element of verbal influence being unobvious. A distinctive feature of suggestiveness is the absence of conscious control over the processing of the received information.

There is a whole range of linguistic devices that have the ability to influence people and bring certain meanings and shades of meanings to the forefront [9,

p. 474]. Thus, metaphor is often used as a tool to present the situation in a favorable way to the listener. As noted by the above authors, antithesis is also one of the techniques that effectively fulfill the function of persuasiveness. Politicians often use the antithesis "we □ them" to create in the minds of listeners the idea of division between their own and strangers [10, p. 256]. Another means of realizing the function of persuasiveness is the use of emotionally evaluative words called affects. They can be construed as emotive intensifiers that intent to appeal to the values of the audience and possessing the ability to ascribe to the speaker various personal attributes of an axiological nature, such as wisdom, restraint, religiosity, and so forth [11, p. 477]. Such words are used in order to prevent rational thinking on the part of the listener and influence them suggestively without giving away the explicit intention to do so.

The means of persuasiveness also include euphemisms, which help to create a certain picture in the listener's mind, because when things are not called by their names, a certain impression of taboo, negative meaning of unnamed phenomena is created. In addition, such techniques as nominalization, i.e. depersonalization of a sentence in order to remove responsibility and shift the focus to ideology, which makes it easier to manipulate consciousness, can also be used [2, p. 344]. Or vice versa, politicians often use such means as intimization and dialogization, which are aimed at creating an impression of closeness and similarity of opinions and goals between them and the recipients of information, which helps to win the public to their side. There are many linguistic means that fulfill the function of persuasiveness, but in political discourse they are used most often, as politics is based on contact and communication with society. They help to create a certain image of a politician and to achieve the set goals.

The origins of political advertising

Touching upon the subject of history of political advertising, it emerged at the time when politics itself emerged, when states needed to enter into a dialog with the people, they used it as a way to influence the population [12, p. 16].

² Sheigal E.I. Semiotics of political discourse // [Electronic resource]: Student Archive File archive // Volgograd State Pedagogical University. 2000. URL: <https://studfile.net/preview/4584817/> (date of reference 19.01.2024).

Political advertising both in Russia and in the West developed most actively in periods of instability, conflicts and wars. This is due to the fact that it is precisely at such times that politicians need to gain the support of the people. At first, oral political advertising appeared, when politicians and autocrats made speeches in squares, their envoys addressed people with manifestos and proclamations. Then with the development of new technologies it became possible to print posters, leaflets, cartoons, which combined iconic and textual signs and due to this more actively influenced the minds of people. In the modern world there is every opportunity for the active development of political advertising: television, the Internet, where politicians can place their advertising in any form [13, p. 78-86]. This is actively used in the U.S., while in the UK there are laws restricting political advertising on radio and television.

The *pragmatic function* of such genre of texts is to influence the recipient of the message, call them to action. This goal is achieved by various linguistic devices: adjectives that contain subjective evaluation, drawing upon the contrast between good and bad, the opposition between their own and others. The appellative function is widely used to awaken the spirit of patriotism and performatives to create the image of a politician. When the goal is to ridicule and denigrate the reputation of the opponent, wordplay, colloquial vocabulary, stylistic devices (anaphora, epiphora, rhyme) are used.

Political advertising in the USA: a cultural and linguistic study

Translation of advertising texts requires the translator to possess extra-linguistic information, to perform cognitive processing of complex information, to correctly interpret culturally marked lexical units, allusions, precedent texts, names, etc. In the following paragraphs of the article culture-specific elements used by politicians in their speeches and techniques of their translation will be studied³.

“Somehow prosperity would trickle down, well now we know the truth, instead of prosperity trickling down, pain has travelled up.”

Каким-то образом богатство, как тонкая струя, польется сверху вниз, но теперь мы знаем правду, этого не случилось и боль распространилась повсюду, как прорванная дамба.

This is referring to the concept of "trickle-down economics", i.e. “экономика просачивающегося богатства”, which is about cutting taxes for corporations, entrepreneurs and the wealthy in order to stimulate economic growth, which will subsequently generate income for the less well-off. Also called "Reaganomics"⁴. The above statement uses metaphor – wealth is identified with water. Remetaphorization (domestication) is selected as the translation technique.

“It will help jumpstart our economy and bring back our Main Streets all across America.”

Это поможет дать толчок нашей экономики, вернуть малый бизнес и трудоустроить средний класс во всех штатах Америки.

Metonymy “Main Street”⁵ has several meanings. Obama uses the term to denote small companies, the owners and employers of which are middle class.

“A moment when our nation is at war, our economy is in turmoil and the American promise has been threatened once more.”

В момент, когда наша страна находится в состоянии войны, экономика переживает кризис и Американская мечта находится под угрозой.

American promise in this particular context means the same as American dream, equal opportunities for all, no matter the social status or financial affairs. The speech called “American Promise” had already been made by president Lyndon Johnson after the Marches from Selma to Montgomery, through which African Americans stood up against their lack of voting rights, and the Obama campaign was based on eradicating racism and developing the African American community (The American Presidency Project). Thus, the precedent text is Lyndon Johnson's “American Promise” speech.

Я представлял, как истории обычных темнокожих сливаются с историями о Давиде и Голиафе, Моисеи и Фараоне, Даниил и ров со

³ All examples throughout the article were selected by the author from recordings of speeches, as well as from newspapers. The translation is also done by the author.

⁴ Will Kenton Trickle-Down Theory [Electronic resource] // Investopedia. 2021. URL: <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/t/trickledowntheory.asp> (date of reference 16.01.2024).

⁵ Cambridge Dictionary [Electronic resource] // URL: <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/main-street?q=main+street+> (date of reference 18.01.2024).

львами, Долина сухих костей в Иезекииля (Библия центр).

Obama often refers to the Bible in his election campaigns, as a way to appeal to Christian voters. The translation technique is to adapt the text in SL to TL using the official translation of the Bible into Russian, stylistic device used by Obama is allusion.

“...and a king who took us to the mountaintop and pointed the way to the promise land. Yes we can to justice and equality.”

...и король, который привел нас на вершину горы и указал путь к Земле обетованной. Скажем «да» справедливости и равенству.

This is in reference to the last speech of Martin Luther King called “I’ve been to the mountaintop” made in 1968. The mountain symbolizes Mount Sinai, where the Ten Commandments were given to Moses. Obama addresses King’s speech, whom he calls “король” (king). It is clear that Obama uses the word meaning MLK because of the indefinite article “a”. This is an example of word play.

“On one end of the spectrum, we’ve heard the implication that my candidacy is somehow an exercise in affirmative action...”

На одном конце спектра нам говорят, что моя кандидатура является результатом позитивной дискриминации...

Affirmative action (позитивная дискриминация) is a U.S. policy that grants special privileges to social groups that have been discriminated against. The term was first used in U.S. Executive Order 10925 during the J. Kennedy administration in 1961⁶. This is an example of a culture-specific element in the text. The best translation technique is explication since there is no such thing in Russian.

“...and just hope that it fades into the woodwork.”

...и надеяться, что проблема просто исчезнет.

Fade into the woodwork – an idiom that means that someone or something becomes invisible, hides,

or disappears⁷. The expressiveness was lost in translation due to lack of equivalent idiomatic expression in TL that would not change the style of the speech.

“...passed on from an earlier generation that suffered under the brutal legacy of slavery and Jim Crow.”

...унаследованное от предыдущих поколений, которые страдали под гнетом ужасных последствий рабства и расовой сегрегации.

After the end of the American Civil War, African Americans were freed from slavery and given rights, and in response, southern states began passing local laws that seriously oppressed them. These were given the unofficial name “Jim Crow Laws” («Законы Джима Кроу») ⁸. Jim Crow is a character in a racist caricature of black people by Thomas D. Rice. A culture-specific element, a reference to racial laws in the USA.

“Segregated schools were and are inferior schools; we still haven’t fixed them, 50 years after Brown v. Board of Education.”

Школы, созданные исключительно для афроамериканцев, были и остаются низшего уровня. Спустя 50 лет после признания судом неконституционности раздельного обучения белых и афроамериканцев, они все еще существуют.

Brown v. Board of Education (Браун против Совета по образованию) is a legal case in which in 1954 the U.S. Supreme Court declared the separation of white and black schools illegal⁹.

In this case, explication is necessary in translation because not every Russian-speaking recipient is familiar with the above described element. Moreover, the method of concretization to correctly convey the meaning of the words “fixed them” was applied.

And you know, Senator McCain, I think the “Straight Talk Express” lost a wheel on that one.

И знаете, сенатор МакКейн, мне кажется в момент обсуждения этого вопроса ваш знаменитый «Прямолинейность экспресс» сошел с рельс.

McCain prided himself on his straightforwardness in answering reporters’ questions. This phrase (Straight

⁶ Britannica, The Editors of Encyclopedia [Electronic resource] // Encyclopedia Britannica. 2021. URL: <https://www.britannica.com/topic/affirmative-action> (date of reference 22.01.2024).

⁷ Dictionary, Merriam-Webster, [Electronic resource] // URL: <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/come%20out%20of%20the%20woodwork> (date of reference 22.01.2024).

⁸ Urofsky, Melvin I. “Jim Crow law” [Electronic resource] // Encyclopedia Britannica. 2021. URL: <https://www.britannica.com/event/Jim-Crow-law> (date of reference 2.01.2024).

⁹ Duignan, Brian. “Brown v. Board of Education” [Electronic resource] // Encyclopedia Britannica. 2021. URL: <https://www.britannica.com/event/Brown-v-Board-of-Education-of-Topeka> (date of reference 2.01.2024).

Talk) was in many newspapers along with the senator's name¹⁰. Obama uses a play on words in his metaphor "express lost the wheel"; in the Russian language, the expression "сойти с рельс" is more common.

"And Detroit had dragged its feet too long in terms of getting that done."

И основные производители автомобилей в стране тянули с выполнением этой задачи слишком долго.

In this example the collective word Detroit, a city in the state of Michigan that is synonymous with America's automobile industry, is used to denote car manufacturers, which is a metonymy (Cambridge Dictionary).

"I am somebody who believes that Roe versus Wade was rightly decided."

Я верю, что легализация абортс была верным решением.

Roe v. Wade is a landmark 1973 Supreme Court decision that ruled that abortion is a constitutional right for women¹¹.

As in the example of Brown v. Board of Education, explication is necessary in translation.

"Unfortunately, they left the money behind for No Child Left Behind."

К сожалению, они отстали при определении бюджета для законопроекта «Ни одного отстающего ребенка».

The bill was signed into law in 2001 under George W. Bush Jr. and required each state to develop a background check system¹².

"This has not been Mr. Oil or Mr. Gas or Mr. Coal."

«Он не будет развивать нефтяную, газовую или угольную промышленность».

Romney stated that Obama will not develop the above industry, saying he is not Mr. Oil/Gas/Coal. It is a common technique in English-speaking culture to assign a name to a person according to their beliefs/qualities, e.g. Miss Congeniality - creating pseudo-anthroponyms. This is usually not done in Russian, especially in speeches by government officials, therefore, an acceptable translation technique

would be explication which would lead to loss of expressiveness, or compensation, which means that a stylistic device would be added in TL where there is none in SL.

"China ate your lunch, Joe."

Китай обвел тебя вокруг пальца, Джо.

Take someone's lunch money, eat someone's lunch – an allusion to America's culture of bullying in schools. This is what China did to America in the negotiations.

"Pigs in the blanket... fry them like bacon."

Поросята в одеяле... поджарим их, как бекон.

In America, the word "pig" is used to mean policemen. Pigs in a blanket is analogous to a dish known in Russian culture as "сосиска в тесте" (sausage in dough). Trump is referring to comments about police made by African Americans during protests by the Black Lives Matter movement.

In conclusion to the previous paragraph it can be said that the most used means of expressiveness are: metaphor, anaphora, epiphora, metonymy, word-play, lexical repetition, idioms and colloquial expressions, rhyme, jargonisms and biblical allusions are also present. The main methods of translation are lexico-grammatical transformations, such as explication, concretization, domestication of metaphors, and others, which will further be discussed in the conclusion part of the article. Stylistic devices, such as anaphora, epiphora, etc., were translated into Russian using the most suitable technique that would communicate them, as these stylistic devices are key to the pragmatic function of political advertising.

Political advertising in the UK: a cultural and linguistic study

In this paragraph of the current article, the political advertising discourse of UK politicians will be examined. Despite some limitations of television advertising and the later, relative to the USA, introduction of the practice of pre-election debates, political advertising in the UK has existed for a long time and in terms of strategies, techniques, including linguistic ones, does not differ much from the US political advertising.

¹⁰ Dan Balz McCain Rides 'The Straight Talk Express' [Electronic resource] // 1999. URL: <https://www.washingtonpost.com/wp-srv/politics/campaigns/wh2000/stories/mccain090299.htm> (date of reference 05.01.2024).

¹¹ Britannica, The Editors of Encyclopedia [Electronic resource] // Encyclopedia Britannica. 2021. URL: <https://www.britannica.com/event/Roe-v-Wade> (date of reference 6.01.2024).

¹² Duignan, Brian and Nolen, Jeannette L. [Electronic resource] // Encyclopedia Britannica. 2021. URL: <https://www.britannica.com/topic/No-Child-Left-Behind-Act> (date of reference 6.01.2024).

"We are not talking peanuts."

Речь идет не о малой сумме.

Peanuts – in British slang, a paltry sum of money¹³.

"...Where things start to go pear shaped again."

Когда ситуация снова начнет ухудшаться.

To go pear shaped – colloquial expression in British English, meaning to go wrong.

"Black Wednesday cost Britain 3.3 billion"

Черная среда, когда курс фунта резко упал, стоила нам 3,3 млрд.

A culture-specific element that requires explication by addition.

"We're going to get rid of some of these quangos..."

Мы избавимся от некоторых бесполезных полуавтономных неправительственных комитетов...

Quango - quasi-autonomous national government organization – An organization partly controlled and funded by the government but operating independently of it. A culture-specific element.

"A proper replacement for Trident."

Достойная замена существующей ядерной программе.

Trident is the name of the program. The title was omitted and the meaning was explicated.

About 1 in 50 jobs are zero hours contracts.

Договор с нефиксированным минимумом рабочих часов заключается при поступлении на 1 работу из 50.

Zero hours contracts – a contract where the employer is not obliged to provide a fixed minimum of working hours, but at least 8 hours must be worked per month, i.e. the employee can be paid for one working day in a whole month. Such contracts are predominantly used in the UK. An explication of the culture-specific element is needed.

Tories have got sod-all to offer the young.

Консерваторы не могут предложить молодежи ни черта.

Sod-all – a crude British colloquial expression meaning a total absence of sth¹⁴.

We can't go on like this. With suspicious minds¹⁵.

Нельзя так продолжать...жить в подозрениях.

Suspicious minds is an Elvis Presley song. The poster shows D. Cameron with the singer's famous hairstyle. It's about Cameron having his face so re-touched that he's probably more concerned about his own celebrity status than politics.

We can't go on like this. Can't you hear it? The drums, the drums, the never-ending drums.

Нельзя так продолжать... Неужели вы не слышите? Барабанная дробь, барабанная дробь, точно как в Докторе кто, она никогда не затихает.

A reference to the famous Doctor Who series. The drumming was a signal of threat and danger. An explication was made during translation.

Don't let him take Britain back to the 1980s.

Не позволяйте ему вернуть Британию в 1980-е.

David Cameron is pictured on the hood of an Audi Quattro, the car popularized by the 80s British TV series Ashes to Ashes.

Fire up the Quattro. It's time for change¹⁶.

Заводи Quattro. Едем на встречу перемена.

I've never voted Tory before, and never would because that evil cow stole my milk.

Я никогда не голосовал за консерваторов, и дальше не буду, потому что эта злобная мышь забрала у меня молоко.

Cow – profanity in British Slang¹⁷.

This is about Margaret Thatcher, former Conservative Prime Minister, abolishing the provision of free milk in schools for children over the age of 7.

A toff on crime. A toff on the causes of crime.

Аристокрах в борьбе с преступностью. Аристокрах в борьбе с причинами преступности.

¹³ Cambridge dictionary [Electronic resource] // URL: <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/peanuts> (date of reference 12.01.2024).

¹⁴ Dictionary, Merriam-Webster, [Electronic resource] // URL: <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/sod%20all> (date of reference 12.01.2024).

¹⁵ The Guardian, [Electronic resource] // URL: <https://www.theguardian.com/politics/2010/jan/30/david-cameron-graffiti> (date of reference 12.03.2024).

¹⁶ Flickr, [Electronic resource] // URL: <https://www.flickr.com/photos/conservatives/4486832262> (date of reference 12.03.2024).

¹⁷ The Britannica Dictionary [Electronic resource] // URL: <https://www.britannica.com/dictionary/cow> (date of reference 12.01.2024).

A toff – a person belonging to the upper class. Consonant with the word “tough”. This is what Cameron promised to be in relation to crime¹⁸. The British press often mentioned Cameron's upper-class background and privilege. These two ideas find reflection in the derisive text. In the translation, I decided to combine two words: аристократ – toff and крах – failure which in this case reflects the meaning of the word “tough” while retaining the similarity to the word “аристократ”.

Vote conservative actually.

Реальный голос за консерваторов.

An allusion to the popular British movie *Love Actually*. In this advertisement, B. Johnson recreates a scene from this movie and at the same time calls to vote for him. Since the movie is called *Real Love* in Russian (*Реальная любовь*), this expression was conveyed as “Real voice for the conservatives” («реальный голос за консерваторов»).

Marmite, yes or no?

Бутербродные пасты, за или против?

Marmite – the name of the brand that produces these pastes in the UK. Metonymy was used in the translation, as the Russian-speaking audience would not be familiar with this brand.

According to the results of the study of different types of political advertising in the UK, it is evident that the most frequently used means of expressiveness are: metaphor, irony, wordplay, colloquial expressions. Many culture-specific elements are present. Translation methods similar to those mentioned above were used in translation. The main difference between the language of political advertising in the UK and the USA is the absence of biblical allusions and jargonisms in the former.

Conclusion

The politicians' speeches are characterized by frequent use of metonymy, idioms, lexical repetition, colloquial vocabulary, allusions to the founding fathers, metaphors, irony, parallelism, references to literary works, hyperbole, gradation, anaphora, epiphora, and epithets. In American debates there is jargon, culture-specific elements are widely represented, such as famous court proceedings, characters from famous TV shows, television networks, racial topics, government

programs, represented by abbreviations, most often having no equivalents in Russian, toponyms.

British politicians' TV commercials use slang, idioms, coarse colloquialisms.

Cartoons and posters have a similar set of linguistic devices. They use homophones, homographs, idioms, word play, rhyme, contamination, colloquial vocabulary, vocabulary from different fields, e.g. sports, medicine, slang, parallelism, irony, adaptation of well-known texts, in particular prayers, to suit the necessary messages, cultural elements (movies, musicians, literary works).

Lexico-grammatical transformations were used for translation, such as concretization and generalization to translate metonymy. Descriptive translation and explication to translate culture-specific elements and names of court proceedings and government programs. Hyperboles, gradation, anaphora, epiphora, and epithets were translated according to the principle of preserving these stylistic means in the Russian language in order to complete the pragmatic function. For the translation of jargonisms, slang and common parlance, the method of selecting stylistic and semantic equivalents was used. Abbreviations were translated by means of explication and addition in the absence of an equivalent in Russian.

To translate the linguistic means used in cartoons and posters, methods of substitution of concepts with similar ones were used. When translating these types of political advertisements, I was guided primarily by the principles of preserving their pragmatic function, i.e. comic transmission of the message with the preservation of linguistic characteristics of wordplay, rhyme, contamination, and the principle of preserving the unity of text and image, the method of substitution of concepts with similar or related ones was widely used. Their stylistic and semantic equivalents in Russian were used to translate the lexicon of certain fields, cultural elements, and prayers. Some culture-specific elements were adapted for the Russian-speaking recipient. In some cases stylistic devices could not be relayed, then the method of approximate translation was used, which led to the loss of imagery and expressiveness.

The least used translation methods are calque translation, transcription and transliteration, as they

¹⁸ Cambridge dictionary [Electronic resource] // URL: <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/toff> (date of reference 12.01.2024).

would not be suitable for political advertisements, in particular those cited in the article, due to the fact that the employment of such techniques would result in an unsuccessful translation from the perspective of the pragmatic function – specifically, the function of persuasion. Advertisements are deliberately crafted to elicit a particular effect on the audience, no technique is accidental, so each of them should be reflected in the translation.

Stylistic devices in public oriented texts are a very broad subject that needs to be studied extensively. The examples reviewed in the current article are part of a continued research in the fields of translation, linguistics and culturology in correlation with linguistic identity. The findings of the study can be used in the aforementioned fields, as well as multitude of others, for various purposes.

References

1. Kuznecov, P.A. (2015) *Politicheskaya reklama. Teoriya i praktika: ucheb. Posobie [Political advertising. Theory and practice: textbook]*. Moscow: "YUNITI-DANA". (In Russ.).
2. Teun, A van Dijk (2008). *Discourse and Power*. UK: Bloomsbury Publishing.
3. Sokolova, O. V (2014). *Tipologiya diskursov aktivnogo vozdejstviya: poeticheskij avangard, reklama i PR [Active Effect Discourses. Poetic avant-garde, advertising and PR]*. Moscow: "Gnosis". (In Russ.)
4. Horoshkevich N.G. (2015). *Social'naya i politicheskaya reklama: uchebno-metodicheskoe posobie [Social and Political Advertising: Educational and Methodological Manual]*. Ekaterinburg: UrFU. (In Russ.).
5. Bushev A.B. (2018). Yazykovie osobennosti reklamnogo, politicheskogo i PR-diskursov [Linguistic peculiarities of advertising, political and PR discourses]. (review). *Social sciences and Humanities. Domestic and foreign literature. Ser. 6. Linguistics: Abstract journal*. (In Russ.).
6. Moshcheva, S.V. (2014). Politicheskij reklamny diskurs: intentsionalny aspekt [Political advertising discourse: intensional aspect]. *Udmurt univ. version. Iss. 2, History and Philology*. (In Russ.)
7. Filimonova, E. A., Ryukova, A. R. (2016). Yazykoviye sposoby realizatsii persuzivnosti [Linguistic ways of realizing persuasiveness]. *Bashkir University Bulletin*, 21 (2), 431-435. (In Russ.)
8. Chernyavskaya, V. E. (2003). Medial'ny povorot v lingvistike: polikodoviye i gibridnye teksty [Medial turn in linguistics: polycode and hybrid texts]. *ISU Herald*, 122-127. (In Russ.)
9. Boldyrev, N.N. (2021). Kognitivnye issledovaniya yazyka [Cognitive language research]. Kognitivnye issledovaniya estestvennoj kommunikacii: Qs&As: *materialy kruglogo stola [Cognitive studies of natural communication: Qs&As: proceedings of the round table]*, 1 (44). Tambov: "Derzhavinskij". (In Russ.)
10. Mihalyova, O. L. (2009). Politicheskij diskurs: Specifika manipulyativnogo vozdejstviya [Political discourse: Specifics of manipulative influence]. Moscow: "Librokom". (In Russ.)
11. Karasik, V.I. (2002). *Yazykovej krug: lichnost', koncepty, diskurs [The Language Circle: Personality, Concepts, Discourse]*. Volgograd: "Peremena". (In Russ.)
12. Egorova-Gaatman, E.V., Pleshakov, K.V. (1999). *Politicheskaya reklama [Political Advertising]*. Moscow: "Nikkolo M". (In Russ.).
13. Rybak, M.V., Krylova, T.V. (2023). The use of cultural aspects of advertising texts for the formation of intercultural competence among higher education students. *Service plus*, 17(1), 78-86. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7992394